

ISic0308

Letter of Iulius Paternus to the Emperors Marcus Aurelius and Lucius Verus

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,William Szymanski,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.03.23

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

The main fragment was found in 1741 in the area of the Duomo , and given by Giuseppe Paternò to Ignazio Paternò Castello, Prince of Biscari, shortly afterwards. The smaller fragment was first recorded in 1769.

Coordinates

37.502351, 15.087629

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 538

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of a white marble tablet. The larger fragment is intact along the upper edge, but broken left and right. The lower edge is uneven and corroded. The smaller fragment is broken or eroded on all sides, but preserves part of the right margin. Both fragments are highly finished on the reverse. The larger fragment preserves a raised margin along the upper edge of the reverse. Faint traces of a similar raised margin on the lower right corner of the reverse of the smaller fragment suggest the stone is more or less complete bottom right, but the text could have continued on a second stone below. If the restoration of the Emperors' titles in line 1 is correct, then approximately half the stone is missing on the left side. Some letters are lost from the right margin over the first few lines.

Dimensions

Height 30.5 cm

Width greater than 53 cm

Depth 3.8-4.2 cm

Layout

Latin text preserved over 12 lines. The first line is in slightly larger and more widely spaced letters. The text closes up over lines 2 and 3, with a more or less regular size and spacing over the rest of the stone. Interpuncts are used sparingly in the text, and their placing appears deliberately intended to emphasise certain elements. The letters are neatly cut, with limited serifs (but sometimes substantial feet to vertical strokes), and a tendency towards the taller narrower letters common from the second/third centuries AD onwards; this is particularly noticeable with the letter E, which is not always easy to distinguish when corroded. Tall 'I' is employed. P is generally open.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1-12: 10-21 mm

Interlineation

Not recorded: mm

Text

1. [AntoninoetVeroAugg(ustis)Arme]ñiacis · suis · Iulius · Paternus · sa[lutem]
2. [---]es · pertulisse[m] ut se haberet opus por[tus][]
3. [---]m propitii velitis admittere ita me cu[r]ia[]
4. [---]o vestro in eadem cura remanere deberem, q[u][a re]
5. [---]reficiendam curavi. Cum deinde Catinenses m[unus]
6. [---]quam · pecuniam · dari iuberetis · rescripsi. Set Sei[us]
7. [---]nummos subministratum · id q(ue) ipsum etiam
8. [---]m dari ipsis · iussisset, ut ordine suo scrib[itu]ra fieret(vac.undefi[n]ed)
9. [---]ram transiret · II · viri consensu paucorum de[c]urionum(vac.undefi[n]ed)
10. [---]cipium. Cum erga procuratorem vestrum in[re]verens v[er]
11. [---]te curia ageretur · ingressus petii ut quatenus neque(vac.undefi[n]ed)
12. [---]tratibus neq(ue) magistratus vellent in[ter]mitte[re], ordo[]

Apparatus

Text of Prag based upon autopsy

Translation (en)

Translation (it)

Commentary

Three further fragments of one or more very similar texts (perhaps even part of this text) are also preserved (two were found in the late 18th century, the third was found in via Dusmet in 1958), but the relationship between these remains very uncertain (see ISic0821 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0821>] , ISic1664 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1664>] , ISic3153 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3153>]).

Iulius Paternus was appointed by the Emperors as a curator operis (overseer of public works) for Catania. This letter reports his efforts to complete the works and to resolve a crisis over the funding. The works may have been connected with the harbour (portus, line 2, or porticus? one of the similar fragments describes harbour works). The Catania senators refused to pay their part and the work was completed by Paternus with imperial funds. The imperial procurator (called Seius? the financial officer for the island) subsequently tried to put arrangements in place to ensure the city repaid Paternus for the work. This proposal was resisted by the city duumvirs and a small group of senators (acting 'irreverently' towards the procurator). Paternus intervened further to resolve the dispute. The letter's publication – probably attached to the building

works - will have confirmed that resolution and publicised Paternus's actions.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175763

EDR 139966

EDCS 21900343

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0308. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335091>